

LEADERSHIP QUALITIES OF STUDENTS: THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

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Based on an analysis of scientific research, the author identifies the following leadership qualities that need to be developed in a future teacher in the process of professional training at a university: professional: organizational and managerial qualities, effective communication, cooperation and the ability to work in a team, tolerance, adaptability, innovation; personal: self-confidence, responsibility, discipline, activity and initiative, empathy, desire for self-development and self-improvement.

Keywords: leadership, leader, leadership qualities, future teachers, classification of leadership qualities, educational process at a university, professional and personal leadership qualities.

Reform processes that permeate modern society in all spheres of activity provoke the emergence of new trends, trends in the training of future specialists, including future teachers. Globalization, informatization and digitalization contribute to the optimization of the educational process on the one hand, but on the other hand, the teacher ceases to be the dominant source of information, losing his leading position in the labor market. That is why training a competitive teacher with leadership qualities and capable of creating an innovative educational product is one of the priorities of modern higher education.

The problem of leadership qualities is being actively studied abroad, and the main scientists (W. Bennis, R. Dilts, E. Dearing, A. Lawton, B. Nanus, D. Russell, E. Rose, etc.) include personal and professional ones.

W. Bennis, B. Nanus identify the following leadership qualities: guiding vision (clear understanding of professional and personal goals); inner passion (the desire to take advantage of the opportunities that are presented); integrity of personality; loyalty to one's principles; desire and ability to learn from and work with others; curiosity; willingness to take risks and experiments [1].

According to R. Dilts, D. Russell, leadership qualities should include: communication (the ability to build effective interaction with people); systems thinking (allows the leader to identify and understand the problem space in which he and his colleagues work); strategic thinking (allows you to think through the path along which you need to move towards the intended goal [2].

A. Lawton, E. Rose, N. Huber identify foresight and the ability to see priorities as the most important leadership qualities. In addition, effective communication and the ability to build interpersonal relationships are also priorities for a leader [3; 4]. In turn, A.V. Avdeeva presents the following leadership qualities as components of leadership competence:

- intellectual (manifested in readiness to perform professional tasks, in the ability to generate ideas and move away from standard solutions),
- organizational (expressed in the ability to make decisions independently, voluntarily take responsibility for solving a group problem),

- performance (including readiness to perform long-term work with high efficiency, the ability to find a non-standard solution and adequately evaluate the results achieved);

- socio-communicative (including the ability to lead people, the ability to smooth out conflicts when solving complex problems in a group and find a common language with different people) [5].

L.D. Kuznetsova, V.V. Manikhin, A.S. Ognev talk about leadership competencies, which are based on the following qualities:

- desire for achievement and self-development,
- creativity,
- ability to inspire others;
- managerial qualities, namely: the ability to set goals, forecast, make decisions, and effectively control;
- ability to act in situations of uncertainty;
- social responsibility [6].

In turn, N.A. Kryukova divides the leadership qualities of future specialists into basic and additional. The scientist includes the following in the first category:

- the ability to motivate, inspire people, take care of the team (team) and give it a vision of a common mission;

- the ability to interact in a team, listen to its decisions, and develop it;

- the ability to understand people's psychology, resolve conflicts, find mutual understanding and inspire trust. As we see, we are talking about organizational and communicative competencies. Additional qualities of a leader N.A. Kryukova include:

- research competencies (the ability to conduct scientific analysis to obtain a discovery or other new result);

- intellectual competencies (the ability to think analytically, compare facts, build logical chains to solve a problem);

- information competencies (the ability to find and systematize the data necessary to solve a problem) [7, p. 20-22].

A.V. Evdokimov complements this list with such qualities as ambition and a high level of energy. According to the scientist, a leader is honest with himself and others, confident in himself and his goals [8].

In the work of N.V. Prikhodko we find the following list of personal leadership qualities: communication skills, organizational skills, increased activity, moderate emotionality, pronounced innovation, business and moral qualities.

In the works of foreign researchers we also find a similar list of leadership qualities: motivation to act, organizational skills, effective communication, empathy and emotional intelligence [9; 10; 11].

In the works of E.V. Andrienko characterizes the leadership qualities of an individual taking into account the specifics of pedagogical activity. Thus, the scientist identifies two groups of teacher leadership qualities: communicative (sociability, focus on others, tendency to cooperate, empathy, tact, patience, emotional stability, flexibility in learning new roles, artistry) and professional (high intellectual flexibility, criticality and quick thinking, ability to improvise, self-criticism, independence, initiative and others).

Based on the works of E.V. Andrienko, T.P. Pitina identifies the following groups of teacher-leader qualities:

- organizational (organization, responsibility, ability to integrate group efforts);
- communicative (sociability, flexibility, influence);
- personal (activity, responsibility, independence). The scientist specifies that: “a high level of development of organizational skills helps the teacher to effectively organize the activities of each student and the activities of the group as a whole. The formation of communicative qualities allows the teacher to productively develop interpersonal relationships with students and regulate relationships between students, their parents, and colleagues. Stable and positively oriented personal qualities, such as determination, confidence, responsibility, activity, contribute to the professional self-improvement and personal development of the teacher” [12].

E.I. Prikhodchenko classifies the leadership qualities of future specialists into three groups:

- general management (professional competence, practical thinking, communication, organizational abilities, hard work, willpower, healthy lifestyle, stress resistance, collectivism);
- actual leadership (charismatic, creativity, initiative, empathy, morality);
- specific – characteristic of a certain area [13, p. 54-55].

M.I. Gubanova, G.V. Uglyanitsa identifies two groups of leadership qualities of future teachers: professional business and personal.

Professional and business qualities, according to the scientist, contribute to the organization of joint activities of all participants in the educational process and characterize the instrumental norm of leadership, since this includes the entire range of qualities that reflect the attitude towards one’s profession (activity, determination, perseverance, responsibility, creativity, organization, competence, high intellectual flexibility, criticality and quick thinking, independence, initiative, etc.).

In turn, the effectiveness of communication among participants in the educational process depends

on the formation of personal leadership qualities. Such qualities express the expressive norm of leadership, and they include personality qualities that express a person’s attitude towards other people (kindness, sociability, goodwill, fairness, empathy, attentiveness, responsiveness, love for children, sympathy, tact, patience, self-criticism, sincerity, emotional stability, flexibility in learning new roles, demandingness, etc.) [14, p. 45].

Deeply explores the leadership qualities of students – future specialists – A.V. Avdeev, dividing such qualities into four blocks:

- intellectual: willingness to take responsibility, the ability to generate ideas (creativity), the ability to practically assess the situation; understanding the innovative needs of the economy and the characteristics of future professional activities; mastery of basic techniques and means of influencing the team; ability to use modern means of obtaining, storing, processing and presenting information; use information reasonably and expediently, pay attention to the main thing when organizing work on joint projects;

- organizational: the ability to make decisions independently, take responsibility for solving a group problem; effectively organize your own activities, organize productive personal contacts; have a psychological readiness to work in a team, the ability to find an individual approach to people;

- performance: readiness to perform long-term work with high efficiency; the ability to put forward ideas and outline ways to implement them; the ability to act purposefully, according to a clear algorithm of actions with a persistent desire to achieve the set goal; ability to implement decisions made and adequately evaluate achieved results; possession of basic means of solving professional problems and skills of rational information processing;

- social and communicative: the ability to lead people, the ability to resolve conflicts when resolving a group task and find a common language with different people, feel and understand the emotions of others; the ability to notice characteristic and subtle features of objects and phenomena [5].

Quite interesting, in our opinion, is the study by M.S. Ionova, N.V. Rezepova, where scientists prove the existence of a correlation between a student’s social status in a group and his leadership position. Thus, the “stars” of the group were the undisputed leaders in all respects, while the “rejected” showed the least leadership qualities. In turn, scientists included communication and organizational qualities as leadership qualities [15].

We share the opinion of scientists regarding the need to develop all of the above-mentioned leadership qualities in future teachers, however, we note that it is difficult to form such a wide range of personal qualities at a high level during 4-5 years of study at a university. That is why, the most important task of modern science is to highlight such leadership qualities of future teachers that are directly related to the teacher’s ability to form an initiative and active personality of the student, on the one hand, and, on the other hand, to be competitive in the modern labor market.

Based on a deep analysis of the phenomenon of “leadership” and the category of “leadership qualities,” as well as the list of such qualities among modern teachers, we can state that the most important leadership qualities of future teachers in today’s sociocultural situation include:

- professional: organizational and managerial qualities, effective communication, cooperation and ability to work in a team, tolerance, adaptability, innovation;
- personal: self-confidence, responsibility, discipline, activity and initiative, empathy, desire for self-development and self-improvement.

Thus, we understand the leadership qualities of future teachers as a stable set of personal qualities of a student, which allow him to be the initiator and organizer of various types of socially significant activities, obtain effective results from such activities, and strive for self-development and self-improvement. Based on an in-depth analysis of scientific literature, we identify the following leadership qualities of a future teacher: professional (organizational and managerial qualities, effective communication, cooperation and ability to work in a team, tolerance, adaptability, innovation) and personal (self-confidence, responsibility, discipline, activity and initiative, empathy, desire for self-development and self-improvement).

We see prospects for further research in the characteristics of the identified qualities and the search for ways to form them in the educational space of the university.

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